

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF PARENTAL UNEMPLOYMENT ON THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF THEIR CHILDREN

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Abstract

The employment status of parents, their educational level and family income are three elements that have important implications in the indicators of educational achievements and performance of today's children. Parental employment or unemployment (and therefore income) has a direct impact on children's outcomes. This affects not only the income that children receive, but also the motivation they receive to have the highest possible achievements. This study includes a quantitative research, which aims to identify the impact of parents' unemployment, their educational level on the performance and academic motivation of their children.

The academic performance of children is very important in their personal development, but also in the development of society as a whole. The more cultured and educated the new generation is, the more society will be developed.

Keywords: Unemployment, Educational Level, Academic Performance, Motivation

Introduction

One of the most current problems as well as one of the most troublesome and most tangible phenomena in our country, mainly among young people in Albania, is unemployment. Albania has a worrying level in terms of the number of unemployed individuals. According to the International Labor Organization, unemployed is anyone over 18 years of age who meets the following conditions: able to work, not working, ready for a paid job and looking for a job. The International Labor Organization (ILO) is committed to the promotion of internationally recognized social justice, human and labor rights, pursuing its fundamental mission that social justice is essential for universal and lasting peace. (<https://www.punetjashtme.gov.al/organizata-nderkombetare-e-punes-ilo/>). Unemployment in our country has increased significantly, especially with the loss of the workplace by that part of the employed population, as well as with the increase in the job offer by that part of the population that affects the legal age for employment. Adding here a category of already more educated individuals. The Institute of Statistics reports that based on the labor force survey, it results that there are a total of 208,000 unemployed in Albania, where the majority are men. (<https://www.instat.gov.al/al/statistikat-n%C3%AB-shkolla/papun%C3%ABsia-n%C3%AB-shqip%C3%ABri/>) In addition to the many impacts that this phenomenon has, there is also an impact on the relationship that is created through the unemployment of parents and children. The impact that parents have on their children's lives is very important both in childhood and in the teenage years. Parental employment patterns affect children in many ways, primarily through the effect on family income, but also on the time parents spend with their children. Parental unemployment has a direct impact on children's outcomes because it affects the amount of income, they have available to invest in them. These investments can be educational resources, such as searching for the best schools, buying specific books, computers, smartphones, iPads, etc. or

social and cultural investments including their personality, emotional development, behavioral habits and a variety of other factors (Rettew, 2018).

According to a study that analyzed the impact that parents' socialization had on their children's academic achievement, they concluded that the consequences were both negative and positive at the same time, and this can be used to show the implications that parental unemployment can also have in other aspects of children's development (Brighouse, 2008). Another important and influential element in the parent-child relationship, in addition to the parents' employment status and the resulting income, is their educational level. The latter is thought to be closely related to employment since in general people with higher education levels have better employment prospects and is also closely related to the motivation of children to achieve as high as possible and succeed in various fields. (Kennedy-Moore, 2019). Therefore, in this study, the academic performance of children is analyzed with the influence of parents' employment status, their educational level and family income.

1.2 - Importance

The importance of this study is related to the current situation in our country. An increasingly worrying phenomenon for Albanian families is unemployment, which is related to income and also to the standard of living. Unemployment in a family would inevitably affect many areas of life, but it also has a great impact on children. This study aims to identify the impact of parental unemployment on the academic achievements and performance of their children, as well as the impact of the educational level of parents on the motivation and academic achievements of their children. It is also of particular importance for parents who must understand how much they influence, so they can make more informed decisions regarding the motivation, support, and imposition that they must pass on to their children.

1.3 - Purpose

The purpose of this study is to identify the impact that parents' employment and unemployment have on

today's teenagers aged 13-15 years, and to understand the impact that parental unemployment causes on their children's academic achievements.

1.3.1 - Objectives

- Explaining the relationship between parental unemployment and their children's academic performance.
- To highlight the relationship that the educational level of parents has in the motivation and academic performance of their children.
- Determining the impact that parents' employment status has on their children's academic performance.

1.3.2 - The research questions of the study are:

- 1) What impact does mother's and father's educational level have on their children's academic performance?
- 2) What is the impact of mother's and father's employment status on their children's academic results?
- 3) Does the level of monetary income of the family affect the academic achievements of students at school?

The hypothesis:

H₁ : The educational level of the mother and father affects the academic performance of their children.

The independent variable: Educational level.

The dependent variable: Academic performance.

H₀ : The educational level of the mother and father does not affect the academic performance of their children.

H₂: There is a positive relationship between mother's and father's employment status and their children's academic performance.

The independent variable: Employment status.

The dependent variable: Academic performance.

H₀: There is no relationship between the employment status of mothers and fathers and their children's academic performance.

H₃ : The level of monetary income in the family lowers the level of academic achievement of students in school.

The independent variable: Income level.

The dependent variable: Academic achievements

H₀: The level of monetary income in the family increases the level of academic achievement of students in school.

Parental employment, capital and influence on children

Parental employment and unemployment can have both positive and negative effects on children through the effect that economic, social and cultural capital has on both the individual and family levels. This can be premeditated, such as buying a book or paying for private school, or unexpected, such as the development of unintended expectations and norms that later reflect in children's lives. The human capital that parents have can be very important for their children, not only in the

inheritance of material things but also through imparting knowledge and culture (William Stixrud, Ned Johnson, 2021). Parents' employment or unemployment (and thus income) has a direct impact on their children's outcomes because it affects the amount of income, they have available to invest in their children.

These investments can be educational resources, such as researching the best schools, purchasing specific books, access to bookstores, computers, and the Internet. Parents who have higher economic capital have more opportunities to invest in the social and cultural capital of their children, accompanying them to their friends' (children's) homes, financing trips or visits to theaters, museums and paying for musical instrument lessons (Ruston, 2021).

2.2 Employment, unemployment, cognitive development and education.

Increased income from employment enables parents to invest more in their children's human capital, spending more money on education and training, through the purchase of books, private teachers or non-public education (Matthias Doepke, Fabrizio Zilibotti, 2020). But Weinberg (2001) criticizes this investment model as one that ignores the child's own abilities and decision-making, and suggests that increased income encourages parents to encourage their children through monetary rewards against improved performance and achievement, while parents with lower income cannot do this (Weinberg, 2001).

Living in a low-income family can increase the level of parental anxiety, which can shake the child's social environment, as well as limit cognitive development. Growing up with an unemployed parent can lower the child's own expectations and aspirations, thus passing on a negative model to children, as well as not providing them with the incentive to invest in their own education (Matthias Doepke, Fabrizio Zilibotti, 2019).

But the employment of parents affects not only the economic resources available in the family. Working parents may have less free time to spend interacting with children, reading to them or helping them with homework, which has a negative impact on cognitive development. Parental involvement in the child's education in terms of school attendance, classroom activities, or volunteer work at school can be affected by the fact that the parent is employed, especially partially, since employment takes up a portion of time that could be used for participation in school activities.

Parental employment patterns and the impact on children

The general effect of maternal and paternal employment on children's cognitive and educational achievements is not clear: on the one hand, children may benefit from higher levels of family income, on the other hand, parental employment reduces the amount of time that parents spend with their children. Some studies have not found any short-term or long-term effects between children's academic achievements and mothers' employment, while fathers' employment does not seem to affect children's long-term educational achievements (Gewirtz, 2020). They point out that the amount of time parents spend with their children is not

decisive for children's cognitive development and academic achievement, but it is the quality of time that matters most, and this is very little affected by parental employment. Following the studies carried out under this topic, it is emphasized that children whose mothers work full-time during the first year of their lives have lower cognitive achievements than children whose mothers do not work. Children of highly educated parents may benefit from extended maternity leave, while children of less educated parents may suffer, even educationally. Evidence on the impact of employment-related income on children's educational attainment is mixed. Estimates of the effect of parental employment on children's educational achievement are somewhat contradictory (Dikollari, F. (2014, 02 28). *The impact and consequences of unemployment*. Retrieved from Tirana Observer: <http://www.tiranaobserver.al/cmimi-psikologjik-dhe-shoqeror-i-papunesise/>). The effect that parents' employment has on their children's educational performance depends on the quality of care that children receive from non-parental care. For example, from grandparents, educators, etc. There were no statistically significant differences between full-time and non-working mothers during their children's teenage years. (John, 2011)

Methodology

In this study, quantitative research methods were used. To carry out the quantitative study, self-report questionnaires of the participants were used as a data collection method.

Sample

The population chosen as the sample (representative group) to carry out the study are the pupils of the "Bedrije Bebeziqi" School in Durrës for the year 2023. The total number of the population is 400 students. The frame of the champion is the official list of pupils of the "Bedrije Bebeziqi" School Durrës for the year 2022-2023. The sample was chosen by means of probability, where every student had an equal chance to be included in the sample. In this study, the sample size is 40 pupils who will represent the ages of 13-15 years. For the selection of the sample, simple random sampling was used, for this the register with the names of every pupil belonging to this age group was used. The sample roughly represents the population for those characteristics that I was specifically interested in studying, and in this case, we say that the sample is reliable.

Study instrument

A self-report questionnaire was used in this study. Considering that this study deals with the impact that parental unemployment has on the academic achievements of their children, the most suitable instrument that could be used was this self-report questionnaire.

The questionnaire in this study is composed of 13 questions where the first questions serve to obtain general information about: age, gender, and then follow questions related to parents' education, their work, monthly income for the family, etc. These questions are formulated with alternatives where the participant who will complete the questionnaire is very clear about what is required in the questionnaire, so he will circle the appropriate alternative for him.

Question 13 of this section is related to the respondents' academic performance at school. The subjects listed in this table were: mathematics, literature, Albanian language, natural sciences (chemistry, physics, biology), social sciences (history, geography, citizenship, economics), foreign language, technology, arts (music, art history, visual art), physical education and sports, as well as career and life skills. The answer alternatives for these sets of questions are categorized into four levels, where for each of the subjects, teenagers can choose the option "non-passing"; "below average"; "average" and "above average" depending on the performance they felt they had in each of these subjects.

Reliability and validity of measurements

When defining the questionnaire, I focused on two important elements such as reliability which is about whether or not the questionnaire will produce consistent results at different times and for different choices, as well as the validity of the questions to produce accurate conclusions which are the result of the research factors and not the result of other factors not systematically related to the research and how these conclusions can be generalized. Also, if a scientific research is not reliable, it is not valid. I believe that the validity of this instrument is maximum since there are questions that measure what we intend to measure and the answers will be specified.

RESULTS OF THE STUDY

Question 1. Age?

The sample (representative of the population) chosen belonged to this age group of 13-15 years old who were students in a 9-year school. In the study, 35% (14 people) belonged to the age of 15 years, 33% (13 people) to the age of 14 years and 32% (13 people) to the age of 13 years.

Question 2. Gender?

In the study, the difference between male and female participants was low, trying to develop the questionnaire fairly with an approximately equal number of genders. 58% males (23 males) and 42% females (17 females) participated in this study.

Question 3: The level of education of your parents? Where the alternatives were: No education, Primary, 8 years old, Secondary, University, Postgraduate. It turned out that Mothers: No education 7% (3 people), Primary 2% (1 person), 8 years old 20% (8 people), Secondary 33% (13 people), University 30% (12 people), Postgraduate 8% (3 people). Father: No education 2% (1 person), Primary 5% (2 people), 8 years old 12% (5 people), secondary 40% (16 people), university 33% (13 people), postgraduate 8% (3 people)

Question 4. Occupation of your parents: It turned out that Mothers without work were 32% (13 people), 13% (5 people) work part-time, 55% (22 people) work full-time. Father: unemployed 12% (5 people), works part time 20% (8 people), works full time 68% (27 people).

Question 5. Occupation of your parents:

- From the answers received to this question, it was found that the greatest number of professions held by Mothers was subordinates with 63%, Middle Manager 11%, Senior Manager 11% and Specialist 2%.

- Fathers: 32.5% (13 people) subordinates, 30% (12 people) middle managers, 17.5% (7 people) specialists and 7.5% (3 people) belong to the senior management profession.

6. Monthly family income

Question 6. Monthly income of the family: The result of this question was that a very small percentage of 10% (4 people) had a monthly income below 20.000.

- 20% (8 people) of the respondents had a monthly income of 30.000-50.000
- 15% (6 people) had an income of 50.000-80.000

- 22.5% (9 people) income from 80.000-100.000
- 17.5% (7 people) of the respondents resulted with an income of 100.000-150.000
- Over 150.000 15% (6 people).

7. Your parents live:

Question 7. Your parents live:

The answers received by the students for this question are

- 82.5% (33 people) answered that parents live together.
- 5% (2 people) divorced
- 2.5% (1 person) separated
- 5% (2 people) in emigration
- 5% (2 people) one of the parents is not living

- Only with the parent/parents resulted in 35% (14 people)
- With the parent/parents and sister/brother, 37.5% (15 people)
- Parents, children and grandparents 27.5% (11 people)
- Only with grandparents 0.0%

Question 8. In your family you live with?

9. You spend more time?

10. You have the greatest support from:

Question 11. Which of your parents requires high academic achievement from you the most?

- Mother 32.5% (13 people)
- Father 40% (16 people)
- Neither 27.5% (11 people)

What resulted from the answers to this question was the fact that parents who had a higher level of

education and also a higher employment status were those parents who demanded higher academic achievements in their children. Parents of children who were uneducated and also unemployed were those parents who did not impose or require high academic achievement in their children.

12. Is learning imposed on you by your parents?

The answers received for this question did not have much difference between each other, except here the answer always which had the smallest percentage. The children who claimed to be forced by their parents to learn were the children of those parents who were employed and had a high academic level. The other part

which turned out not to receive any continuous imposition to learn and also to come out with high academic results was the part where the parents were unemployed and this meant that the motivation here was low including also support and imposition for high academic achievements.

13. Academic performance.

	Not passing	Under average	Average	Above average
a. Mathematics	5%	30%	45%	20%
b. Literature	-	12.5%	52.5%	35%
c. Albanian language	7.5%	12.5%	45%	35%
d. Natural Sciences (Chemistry, Physics, Biology)	-	35%	40%	25%
e. Social Sciences (History, Geography)	-	17.5%	55%	27.5%
f. Foreign language	5%	25%	35%	35%
g. Technology	-	7.5%	45%	47.5%
h. Arts (Music, Art History, Visual Art)	-	7.5%	37.5%	55%
i. Physical education and Sports	-	-	27.5%	72.5%
j. Career and Life Skills	-	12.5%	25%	62.5%

Question 13. Mark for each of the subjects or groups of subjects your academic performance:

This question was the question which would relate the impact of parents' unemployment, employment status and their educational level to their children's academic performance. The percentages obtained from the answers of the respondents were mostly at the average level and above the average, this comes as a result of the educational level of the parents and their employment. The other percentages, which include the under-average and not passing level, belong to those children whose parents are unemployed, have a lower educational status, and this is noted to affect the inheritance of knowledge and culture for their children to learn and study.

4.2 Conclusions***Consequences of parental unemployment and their children's academic achievement.***

The low level of family income has a significant impact on the academic achievements of the surveyed students.

The data showed that the children of unemployed parents were those children who had lower academic achievements compared to the rest who had working parents. This was observed to have a direct impact on motivation. Where those parents who were unemployed or without higher education did not support or impose their children to learn in order to have high academic achievements. Also, these children did not receive the greatest support from the unemployed parent, but from the parent who was employed.

What was noticed was that those children whose parents were unemployed or where only one of them worked part-time, which is necessarily related to the level of income, were the children with very low academic achievements such as in scientific subjects as well as in social ones.

Conclusions on parents' educational level and children's academic performance.

The data showed that the higher the level of education of the mother and father, the higher the academic achievements of the surveyed young people.

Exceptions are subjects such as arts or music which require innate talents rather than cultivated skills in achieving a satisfactory performance. The higher the educational level of the mother, the higher the academic performance of their children.

The majority of respondents whose mothers had completed university or postgraduate education reported an above-average performance in mathematics, Albanian language, social studies, foreign language and technology.

The higher the educational level of the father, the higher the academic performance of young people in the subject of literature, Albanian language, foreign language, technology and social sciences where the largest percentage of teenagers who had performance above on average, they had fathers with university or postgraduate education.

Data on academic achievement in the arts did not show significant differences between the level of education of the mother and father and the academic performance of the respondents.

Conclusions on parental employment and children's academic performance.

The father's employment status has more influence on the growth of their children's academic performance compared to the mother's employment status.

The study data demonstrated that children whose fathers worked full time had above average results in the vast majority of subjects.

In general, children whose parents worked full-time were the ones who performed well in school.

4.3 Recommendations

- To organize special programs, dedicated to the provision of psycho-social services in schools, for young people from low-income families, for young people whose parents are unemployed and for young people whose parents have low education.

- Parental motivation should not be missing, including parents who are employed, unemployed, with a high level of education or a low level of education.

- Increase studies on the unemployment and employment status of parents by linking them to how they affect the motivation and academic achievements of children.

- To conduct studies to see the relationship between these variables: parental unemployment and children's academic achievements, but be conducted with a larger sample number and applied to several different schools.

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